

DIDACTIC ANALYSIS OF THE PROCESS OF ORGANIZING AND CONDUCTING PROFESSIONAL INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM

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Abstract. *This article highlights the unique aspects of organizing and conducting independent education based on the features of the courses and specialties prepared in the credit module system and differences were analyzed didactically.*

Keywords: *credit module, independent education, independent work, education, education.*

In our work, we have covered various aspects of the process of chemistry education and improving its quality in detail [1-10].

This article is devoted to the study of pedagogical and psychological conditions for the implementation of independent education in the updated educational system.

Today, due to the strong flow of information and new technologies, the amount of knowledge that humanity needs to master is also increasing. According to statistics, the amount of knowledge accumulated by humanity doubles every

6-7 years [11]. But on the other hand, such a sharp increase leads to the "obsolescence" of the acquired knowledge of specialists. According to the analysis of experts, 15-20% of knowledge is "obsolete" every year [11]. Scientific and technical progress creates the need to keep the educational system in step with the times, to fulfill the task of training competitive personnel based on the needs of the market economy. The new, modern credit-module system of education implemented in the educational system is a proof that the proverb "Seek knowledge from the cradle to the grave" is not in vain. [1].

The credit-module system assumes that each of the students will receive an individually oriented education based on their abilities and interests, and have equal opportunities in this. Proper organization of students' independent learning process in the credit-module system is one of the most important pedagogical problems of modern education. It is necessary to emphasize how appropriate the phrase "rgat" is. Today's education requires not just teaching the student, but research and development of the psychological and pedagogical conditions necessary for the student to study. That is, the traditional "teaching" process in modern education is being replaced by a new "learning". In this case, the student should not be a passive consumer of the taught knowledge, but should become an active creator of knowledge who, based on the acquired knowledge, has his own position on any issue related to science, can analyze the problem, approach the problem critically, and search for its solutions. It is known from psychology that the human brain is structured in such a way that it quickly forgets or does not accept information that it considers unnecessary and unwanted. Therefore, it is important for students to study their specialties based on their interests and abilities without wasting their valuable time.

Today, one direction of the reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan is related to the introduction of the credit-module system of the organization of education in educational institutions. In this regard, a number of normative and mandatory documents were adopted. According to the "Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" established by the decree of October 8, 85% of higher education institutions in the country are planned to gradually transition to the credit-module system until 2030. In addition, the Republic of Uzbekistan

Laws "On Education" and "On the National Personnel Training Program", President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PF-4947 "Uzbekistan Decree on the Action Strategy for Further Development of the Republic, PQ-2909 of April 20, 2017 "On Measures for the Further Development of the Higher Education System" and PQ of June 5, 2018 - No. 3775 Decisions "On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in comprehensive reforms implemented in the country", Higher and secondary special education Ministry of Education No. 233 of March 27, 2020 "On the introduction of distance education in higher education institutions" and April 10, 2020 "Effective continuation of the educational process in higher education institutions through distance education" Order No. 257 "On the continuation and completion of the 2019/2020 academic year" lays the foundation for improving the education system in our country. Also, the International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan "Instructions on organization and control of independent work of students and undergraduates", "Instructions on graduate work", "Pedagogical work of students of the International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan" "Instructions on the practice" and "Instructions on writing a course work" are the regulatory and legal basis for the proper organization of independent educational activities in Uzbekistan.

Successful implementation of the credit-module system allows training of highly qualified personnel necessary for the society and competitive in the ever-growing labor market. One of the most important priorities for solving this problem is the continuity of personnel training, improving the quality of education, ensuring the investment attractiveness of the education system, and bringing quality education to the level where everyone is equally covered.

Solving this problem requires, first of all, researching the theoretical foundations of the independent education process.

Our didactic analysis shows that some researchers confuse the concepts of independent education and independent work in some cases.

Independent education is an important and integral part of the educational process, which enables students to acquire independent knowledge, freely analyze the topic, have their own opinion on a relevant issue, scientific research, free thinking, problem solving contributes to the formation of necessary knowledge and skills related to the ability to develop conclusions and proposals and their implementation in practice. A student's independent work is a set of educational works specified in the curriculum for mastering a specific subject.

The student's independent work is a systematic activity aimed at mastering a certain part of the knowledge, skills and qualifications specified in the curriculum and the science program from a specific subject, based on the advice and recommendations of the subject teacher, in the classroom and outside the classroom. Although the term "independent education" is widely used in practice, different researchers give different definitions to this concept, and a single definition of this concept has not yet been given in scientific pedagogical literature. It should be said that this

concept is more comprehensive than the concept of independent work. But all the definitions given in the scientific literature essentially go back to a single content: independent education is a systematic activity of a student aimed at acquiring knowledge independently without the direct support of a professor-teacher within a specific subject. It requires the student to concentrate both mental and practical activities. Its result is reflected not only in the student's level of knowledge, but also in his skill and talent. It is the student's psychological characteristics such as self-management, self-activation, self-organization, self-development, self-control develops.

So, independent education is a set of educational, research, scientific research works performed by the student on the basis of the assignment and methodical guidance of the teacher in the relevant subject, but without his direct support. The result of independent education it leads to the formation of the necessary skills and qualifications based on the knowledge of the relevant subject in the student. Also, the aim of independent education is to achieve fundamental knowledge, professional skills and abilities by forming research activities, creativity, independence, organization, and responsibility skills in the future specialty of students. . Also, the main goal of the student's independent work is to organize the student's continuous study of subjects during the semester under the direct guidance and supervision of the professors of the department, to strengthen the acquired knowledge and skills by deep study, to prepare for future classes, to mentally is to form a work culture, independent development and acceptance of new knowledge, and thus achieve the development of highly qualified competitive specialists6.

The main goal of the student's independent work is to form and develop the knowledge and skills necessary for the student to independently perform certain educational tasks under the guidance and control of the teacher 5.

In this way, the authors of the article are able to clearly define the similarities and differences between the concepts of independent education and independent work. Therefore, independent education is the systematic activity of a student in the process of acquiring new knowledge, skills and abilities in the classroom or outside the classroom. independent work of the student is the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the implementation of this activity.

REFERENCES

1. M. Nishonov, N. Holiqova. The importance of using educational resources in independent learning of chemistry. Scientific newsletter of Namangan State University. Namangan 2022. No. 3, pp. 80-83.
2. M. M. Yunusov, M.Nishonov. Studying the Efficiency of Teaching the Chemical Technology Course Using Information Technologies. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching, (2022). 13,33–38.
3. M.Nishonov, Sh.Mamajonov, V.Xujaev – Kimyo o'qitish metodikasi. Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 2002.
4. Карпенко М. П. Перспективы развития системы высшего образования на основе «Концепции вуза– 2030» / М. П. Карпенко //Вестник РЕАН. 2005. Т. 5. №3. С. 27–34